

Photometric Studies of Dysprosium(III) with Gallein

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The formation of reddish coloured complex of dysprosium with gallein has been studied. Dysprosium forms only one complex with gallein at pH 3.5 having λ_{\max} 460 nm. The composition of the complex formed, studied by various methods, is found to be 1 : 1 (M : R). The values of stability constants are also calculated and the average value of log K obtained is 4.0 ± 0.1 . The analytical aspects of the system are also studied and a suitable procedure for the photometric determination of dysprosium using the reagent has been suggested.

GALLEIN, which is 3', 4', 5', 6'-tetrahydroxy fluoran has been recommended for the spectrophotometric determination of indium¹, tin², aluminium³ and antimony⁴. Spectrophotometric determination of consecutive acid dissociation constants of gallein are reported⁵. Reference about the use of gallein as a colorimetric reagent for germanium⁶, gallium and indium⁷, lead⁸ and molybdenum⁹ are also found in literature.

The present paper reports for the first time the complex formation of dysprosium with gallein and its application for the spectrophotometric determination of dysprosium. The complexation of dysprosium with Alizarin S¹⁰, Arsenazol¹¹ and azo derivatives of chromotropic acid¹² are known. Shijo has reported determination of rare earths with trioctyl ethyl ammonium bromide and xylenol orange¹³. A review¹⁴ of the chemical methods of separation and determination of rare earth elements and determination of lanthanides in rocks by photometric method¹⁵ has been reported. References of the analysis of lanthanides when present alone or in mixtures are also found in literature¹⁶⁻¹⁹.

Experimental

The solution of dysprosium(III) was prepared by dissolving a known weight of high purity dysprosium chloride ($\text{DyCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (Indian Rare Earths) in distilled water, acidified suitably with hydrochloric acid. Gallein (supplied by Edward Gurr Ltd., London) was purified. A known weight of the sample was dissolved in alcohol mixture (1 : 1). Freshly prepared and dilute solutions were always used.

Photometric measurements were made on a Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20 colorimeter. Cells of 1 cm pathlength were used for absorbance measurements. All absorbances were noted against distilled water blank. The pH values of the solutions

were maintained and measured with a Elico pH meter (LI-10).

All measurements were made at room temperature. The pH of the solution was maintained by using HCl or NaOH solution. Total volume was maintained to 25 ml in all the experiments. Precipitation was avoided by using dilute solutions of Gallein.

Results and Discussion

Characteristics of the reagent : The effect of pH on the λ_{\max} of the reagent was studied by taking 1.0×10^{-4} M gallein solution at different pH values and studying absorption spectra in the entire visible range. The shift in λ_{\max} with pH is shown in Table-1.

TABLE-1. SHIFT IN λ_{\max} OF GALLEIN WITH CHANGE IN pH

pH	λ_{\max} (nm)
2.5-4.5	420
5.0-9.0	525
10.0-11.0	460

Characteristics of the chelate : The nature of complexes formed was determined by preparing three series of solution containing different ratios of reagent : metal (C/C) as 4 : 1, 1 : 1 and 1 : 4. In each series, ten solutions were prepared and adjusted to different pH values. Their spectra were noted in the entire visible range. The observations obtained were as follows. The concentrations of dysprosium and gallein used in the studies were as below.

- i) dysprosium : gallein = 1 : 4,
M = 1.0×10^{-5} M, R = 4.0×10^{-5} M.
- ii) dysprosium : gallein = 1 : 1,
M = 5.0×10^{-5} M, R = 5.0×10^{-5} M.
- iii) dysprosium : gallein = 4 : 1,
M = 2.0×10^{-4} M, R = 5.0×10^{-5} M.

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For all the three series, in the pH range 2.0 to 4.0, λ_{\max} is 460 nm. In 1 : 1 and 4 : 1 (M : R) mixtures, precipitation was observed above pH 4.5. In the 1 : 4 series, above, pH 4.5 (5.0 to 9.0) λ_{\max} is 525 nm. This corresponds to that of reagent alone at the same pH values, indicating that complex formation does not take place at these pH values. In the pH range 2.0-4.0, there is only one shift in λ_{\max} indicating the formation of only one complex. The studies for the dysprosium system were made at pH 3.5 and absorbances were noted at 460 nm.

Composition of the complex formed: The composition of the complex formed was determined by three different methods, (i) Job's method of continuous variations using equimolar solutions, (ii) mole ratio method and (iii) slope ratio method.

All the three methods show Dy(III)-Gallein chelate to have 1 : 1 (metal : reagent) composition at pH 3.5 and at 460 nm.

Evaluation of stability constant: The values of stability constants were calculated by the following methods (i) method of Foley and Anderson²⁰ modified by Dey and coworkers²¹ using equimolecular solutions and (ii) mole ratio method²². The values of log K obtained for dysprosium-gallein chelate at 25° and at pH 3.5 are 4.7 ± 0.1 and 5.2 ± 0.1 by the respective methods.

Analytical studies of the complex: The colour formation of dysprosium with gallein is instantaneous. There is hardly any change in absorbance even after 24 hours of standing. Temperature change also had no effect and colour intensity remains stable in the range of 10 to 50°. Reagent should be at least four fold excess to have maximum colour formation.

The values of sensitivity and molar absorptivity are $0.065 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ (Sandell's) and 6.48×10^3 litre per mole per cm. The concentration within which Beer's law is followed was found to be 2.6 to 29.5 μg of dysprosium per ml. The effect of foreign ions on the absorbance value of the system was studied. For this various standard solutions of anions and cations were prepared. The tolerance limit of the ion was calculated at that concentration where a change of $\pm 2\%$ in absorbance was noted. Most of the anions and cations were found to be tolerated to a sufficiently fair concentration. But Cu^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Al^{3+} , CH_3COO^- and CO_3^{2-} caused serious interference. Other lanthanide elements also interfere and should be absent in the determination of dysprosium. The tolerance limit of other ions (in ppm) was found to be as follows :

Mn^{2+} (132),	Mg^{2+} (88),	Zn^{2+} (236),	Cd^{2+} (223),
Co^{2+} (71),	Ni^{2+} (87),	Ca^{2+} (64),	Ba^{2+} (164)
Sr^{2+} (90),	Ga^{3+} (25),	In^{3+} (20),	Ti^{3+} (20),
Hg_2^{2+} (28),	Cr^{3+} (40),	Oxalate^{2+} (35),	PO_4^{3-} (76),
I^- (406),	Br^- (384),	$\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ (158),	Citrate^{3-} (76),
SO_3^{2-} (200),	NO_3^- (122),		

Recommended procedure: To the dysprosium solution containing 3 to 29 μg of metal ion, add four fold excess of the gallein solution. Adjust pH to 3.5 and measure the absorbances of the solutions at 460 nm. The absorbance of an unknown sample solution can then be compared with the calibration curve obtained earlier and concentration is determined.

The reagent is reasonably sensitive and can be considered for the photometric determination of dysprosium. The advantage of the method is less interference due to other ions and ease of procedure applied in the determination.

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